

Chemical Investigation of *Pyrus Pashia* Ham

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Pyrus pashia, Ham (Family: Rosaceae) is a medium-sized tree, growing abundantly in the temperate Himalayan region from Kashmir to Bhutan.

The present work deals with the isolation of four different compounds from the light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the bark and leaves. It has been possible to identify (a) Friedelin (0.5%) and β -sitosterol (0.01%) from the light petroleum extract of the dried bark and (b) the hydrocarbon, *n*-triacontane (1%), myricyl alcohol (0.005%), and β -sitosterol (0.04%) from the leaves.

Extraction of the Bark of *P. Pashia*

Air-dried, powdered bark was extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). Chromatographic separation over Brockmann alumina of the solid, obtained after removal of the solvent, furnished two distinct crystalline products:

Fraction (I), m.p. 250-52°, $[\alpha]_D -28.5^\circ$ (CHCl₃), responded to Burchard-Lieberman reaction; it did not exhibit any colour with tetranitromethane. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of friedelin¹⁻³ remained undepressed. The oxime crystallised from benzene, m.p. 290°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of the oxime of friedelin, 290°. (Found: C, 81.33; H, 11.35. Calc. for C₃₀H₅₁ON: C, 81.63; H, 11.56%).

Fraction (II), m.p. 138°, also responded to Burchard-Lieberman reaction and crystallised from methanol. The compound was acetylated and the product was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 126°, $[\alpha]_D -40.5^\circ$ (CHCl₃). The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of the acetate of β -sitosterol remained unchanged. (Found: C, 81.41; H, 11.56. Calc. for C₃₁H₅₂O₂: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%).

It may be noted that from the ethanol extract of the bark a good yield of a red-coloured substance has been obtained which is under investigation.

Extraction of the Leaves of *P. Pashia*

Dried and powdered leaves were extracted with light petroleum (60-80°) and on concentration the extract afforded a semisolid mass which, when chromatographed over Brockmann alumina, furnished three crystalline compounds:

Fraction (I), m.p. 66°, crystallised from light petroleum. (Found: C, 85.38; H, 14.40. Calc. for C₃₀H₆₂: C, 85.31, H, 14.69%). The hydrocarbon was found identical with *n*-triacontane⁴.

1. Drake *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1854, 1570.
2. Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, **27**, 972.
3. Bruun, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 71.
4. Klobb *et al.*, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1910, *iv*, 7, 940.

Fraction (II), m.p. 88°, crystallised from benzene. (Found: C, 82.14; H, 14.21. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{62}O$: C, 82.22; H, 14.15%). IR spectra (nujol): λ_{max} 3300 cm^{-1} .

The chloro derivative, prepared with PCl_5 , was crystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 65°. The chloro derivative was identified to be myricyl chloride⁵.

Fraction (III), m.p. 138°, responded to the Burchard-Lieberman reaction. The acetyl derivative crystallised from acetone, m.p. 125-26°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -41^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate. (Found: C, 81.38; H, 11.24. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%).

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